

Effect of Peer Review Technique on Performance in English Essay Writing among Secondary School Students in Odigbo, Ondo State

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Abstract

The purpose of this research was to investigate the effect of the Peer Review Technique on performance in English essay writing in Odigbo, Ondo State. Two research questions and two null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. A quasi-experimental research design was adopted for the study. Specifically, the non-randomized control group design. The study population consists of all Government Senior Secondary School class two (SSII) students in the 2021/2022 academic session. The sample for the study consists of 160 SSS2 students from two co-educational schools in Odigbo Local Government Area of Ondo State. The experimental group comprised 78 male and female students while the control group comprised 82 male and female students from schools located in rural and urban areas respectively. Both the experimental group and control group were given the same essay writing but the difference is that those in the experimental group were taught essay writing using the Peer Review Technique (PRT), while those in the control group were taught essay writing using the conventional method. The instrument used for data collection was the Essay Writing Achievement Test (EWAT). The data obtained from the trial tests were used to calculate the instrument's reliability using Kendall's formula. It yielded an index of 0.75. Mean was used to answer the research questions while ANCOVA was used to test the hypotheses at $P < 0.05$. From the results obtained, it was found that students in the experimental group had higher performance scores in essay writing than their counterparts who were in the control group. Based on the findings, it was recommended that English language teachers should adopt the Peer Review Technique in teaching essay writing.

Keywords: English in Nigeria, Peer Review Technique, gender, and essay writing

Introduction

The English language remains the cornerstone of education in Nigeria, serving as the primary medium of instruction from upper primary levels through secondary and tertiary education. It functions as the conduit for teaching all other subjects in the curriculum. The challenges of learning English as a second language are widely recognized, particularly in non-English speaking countries like Nigeria. Proficiency in English entails possessing both spoken and written skills for effective communication. As a colonial legacy from the British, English holds a significant position, evident in its status as a mandatory subject in Nigerian senior secondary schools. Across various spheres of Nigeria's development, the English language plays a pivotal role. Nearly all aspects of endeavors beyond individual pursuits necessitate the utilization of English (Olutola, Iliyas & Abdusalam, 2017). Despite the crucial roles attributed to the English language, a significant number of Nigerian students struggle to attain proficiency in its various skills, particularly in the domain of writing. A study by Patrick, Uloh-Bethels, and Ukwueze, (2020) highlights that the underwhelming academic achievements in English among students might be directly linked to their struggles with effective writing. This deficiency in writing skills consequently contributes to subpar performance not only in English but also across other subjects in both internal and external examinations. This trend continues to raise concerns about the broader educational landscape and the holistic development of students. Adding to this discourse, a recent study conducted by Akintunde and Angulu (2020) underscores the enduring nature of the challenges faced by Nigerian students in mastering English writing skills. The researchers found that despite efforts to improve language education, students still grapple with issues of coherence, organization, and grammar in their written expression. This persistent struggle not only affects their academic performance but also hinders their ability to effectively communicate and engage in various professional and social contexts. In the same vein, the performance of students in the English language has been witnessing a consistent decline at both junior and senior secondary school levels. This concerning trend is substantiated by the assessment of the WAEC Chief

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Examiners' Report (2020), which emphasizes that while the questions posed were generally well-suited to the student's abilities, their actual performance did not reflect the expected quality and simplicity of those questions. The report highlights that the students exhibited inadequate essay organization and a lack of conscious effort toward grammatical accuracy. This assessment underscores the observation that despite the accessibility of the questions, students struggled to effectively structure their essays and grappled with grammatical errors, ultimately contributing to their unsatisfactory outcomes.

Notably, the report also draws attention to the students' deficient grasp of the four essential language skills: listening, speaking, reading, and writing—as a significant factor influencing their subpar performance. This observation underscores the pivotal role of these language skills in holistic language proficiency. As such, there arises a compelling need to address these challenges by prioritizing the teaching and learning of essay writing within the framework of the English Language curriculum. Reinforcing the urgency of this matter, recent research by Akintunde and Angulu. (2020) delves into the persistent decline in English language performance among Nigerian students. The study identifies several contributing factors, including limited teacher training, inadequate teaching materials, and a lack of effective instructional strategies. These findings underscore the complexity of the issue and emphasize the necessity for a multifaceted approach to ameliorating the declining state of English language proficiency among students in Nigeria's secondary schools. In light of these insights, a comprehensive overhaul of English language education, particularly in essay writing skills, emerges as an imperative. By addressing the issues highlighted in both the Chief Examiners' Report and recent research, educators, and policymakers can collectively work toward fostering a more effective and enriching learning environment that equips students with the language skills necessary for academic and real-world success. Essay writing, a prevalent linguistic endeavor, serves as a means for individuals to articulate their contemplations on a specific subject (Idris, 2019). Guided by the topic and intent of the writing, this form of composition embodies a distinct content and structure. The author characterizes an essay as a concise written composition addressing a specific theme, highlighting the writer's thoughts through verbal expressions. It not only showcases the writer's proficiency in conveying concepts but also serves as a yardstick for evaluating the writer's intellectual acumen.

Furthermore, recent scholars have emphasized the enduring significance of essay writing in the English curriculum. Okika (2021) and Okon, (2022) underscore its revered status as a staple in exams, often carrying a substantial weightage of marks. This underlines the warranted investment of time and effort into honing essay writing skills. Importantly, the utility of essay writing extends beyond the confines of the English syllabus; it permeates into various subject domains where exam questions frequently assume the essay format. Consequently, students must adeptly tailor their responses to align with the specific essay writing techniques demanded by each question. Strengthening this perspective, Anidi, Obumneke-Okeke, Nwune, and Okwuduba, (2022) acknowledge the multifaceted nature of teaching essay writing. The authors emphasize the essential role of language teachers in providing guidance and control over the sentence structure within essays. This underscores the collaborative effort required to cultivate effective essay-writing skills among students. For second language learners, various impediments can impede students' academic progress. These challenges can be attributed to educators and their instructional approaches, the learning environment, and gender dynamics. In the research by Idris (2019) the absence of modern teaching resources to enhance instruction, inadequate coverage of curriculum content, teachers' limited capacity to deliver effective lessons, and students' struggles to absorb the taught material were identified as obstacles in the realm of English language education. It could be deduced that these same challenges extend to the teaching and learning of essay writing. As highlighted by Akinwumi (2017) essay writing is a notably intricate skill within language acquisition. The optimal approach to mastering this skill involves employing suitable methodologies and allocating substantial time daily for focused instruction. Consequently, the methods employed for its teaching tend to lack innovation and practical orientation, as noted by Nwosu (2017). There are many methods that could be used by teachers in English essay classes. Most teachers have been using the conventional method where the students are arranged in straight lines down and across the classroom. The teacher assumes that all the students in the class have equal knowledge or that they know little or nothing. He stands in front of the class and delivers his lessons. As the teacher dominates the lesson, the students' potentials are rarely used to the fullest and impatience rather than enthusiasm is generated (Nwosu,2017). For language learning, grammatical analysis and rote learning of grammatical rules, vocabulary acquisition, and translation from the target language to the learner's mother tongue and vice-versa are emphasized in the conventional method. The students work individually and are assessed individually. Only the best students are rewarded which forces students to work against each other so as to be the best. As a result of the shortcomings of conventional methods, the researcher intended to investigate the effect of peer review techniques on the achievement of students in English essay writing.

The Peer Review Technique (PRT), devised by linguist Charles James at Johns Hopkins University in 1990 involves collaborative assessment among peers, also known as "peer feedback". This approach entails students reviewing and evaluating

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Based on this disparity of findings on which gender performs better in language, it seems that the exact effect of gender on language performance is not clear; hence there is a need for further studies on the nature of students' performance by gender, especially in Nigeria. English language remains the cornerstone of education in Nigeria, serving as the primary medium of instruction from upper primary levels through secondary and tertiary education. It functions as the conduit for teaching all other subjects in the curriculum. The challenges of learning English as a second language are widely recognized, particularly in non-English speaking countries like Nigeria. Proficiency in English entails possessing both spoken and written skills for effective communication. As a colonial legacy from the British, English holds a significant position, evident in its status as a mandatory subject in Nigerian senior secondary schools. Across various spheres of Nigeria's development, the English language plays a pivotal role. Nearly all aspects of endeavors beyond individual pursuits necessitate the utilization of English (Olutola, Iliyas & Abdusalam, 2017). Despite the crucial roles attributed to the English language, a significant number of Nigerian students struggle to attain proficiency in its various skills, particularly in the domain of writing. A study by Patrick, Uloh-Bethels, and Ukwueze, (2020) highlights that the underwhelming academic achievements in English among students might be directly linked to their struggles with effective writing. This deficiency in writing skills consequently contributes to subpar performance not only in English but also across other subjects in both internal and external examinations. This trend continues to raise concerns about the broader educational landscape and the holistic development of students. Adding to this discourse, a recent study conducted by Akintunde and Angulu (2020) underscores the enduring nature of the challenges faced by Nigerian students in mastering English writing skills. The researchers found that despite efforts to improve language education, students still grapple with issues of coherence, organization, and grammar in their written expression. This persistent struggle not only affects their academic performance but also hinders their ability to effectively communicate and engage in various professional and social contexts. In the same vein, the performance of students in the English language has been witnessing a consistent decline at both junior and senior secondary school levels. This concerning trend is substantiated by the assessment of the WAEC Chief Examiners' Report (2020), which emphasizes that while the questions posed were generally well-suited to the student's abilities, their actual performance did not reflect the expected quality and simplicity of those questions. The report highlights that the students exhibited inadequate essay organization and a lack of conscious effort toward grammatical accuracy. This assessment underscores the observation that despite the accessibility of the questions, students struggled to effectively structure their essays and grappled with grammatical errors, ultimately contributing to their unsatisfactory outcomes. Notably, the report also draws attention to the students' deficient grasp of the four essential language skills: listening, speaking, reading, and writing—as a significant factor influencing their subpar performance. This observation underscores the pivotal role of these language skills in holistic language proficiency. As such, there arises a compelling need to address these challenges by prioritizing the teaching and learning of essay writing within the framework of the English Language curriculum. Reinforcing the urgency of this matter, recent research by Akintunde and Angulu (2020) delves into the persistent decline in English language performance among Nigerian students. The study identifies several contributing factors, including limited teacher training, inadequate teaching materials, and a lack of effective instructional strategies. These findings

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There are many methods that could be used by teachers in English essay classes. Most teachers have been using the conventional method where the students are arranged in straight lines down and across the classroom. The teacher assumes that all the students in the class have equal knowledge or that they know little or nothing. He stands in front of the class and delivers his lessons. As the teacher dominates the lesson, the students' potentials are rarely used to the fullest and impatience rather than enthusiasm is generated (Nwosu,2017). For language learning, grammatical analysis and rote learning of grammatical rules, vocabulary acquisition, and translation from the target language to the learner's mother tongue and vice-versa are emphasized in the conventional method. The students work individually and are assessed individually. Only the best students are rewarded which forces students to work against each other so as to be the best. As a result of the shortcomings of conventional methods, the researcher intended to investigate the effect of peer review techniques on the achievement of students in English essay writing. The Peer Review Technique (PRT), devised by linguist Charles James at Johns Hopkins University in 1990 involves collaborative assessment among peers, also known as "peer feedback". This approach entails students reviewing and evaluating each other's writing, encouraging active participation and dialogue (Okika 2021). Students adopt dual roles as both reviewers and writers, offering diverse perspectives and identifying errors. Unlike conventional one-way teaching, this technique nurtures self-awareness of errors and problem-solving. PRT enhances both spoken and written English proficiency, fostering standard English through teacher and peer guidance during the classroom review process. PRT is premised on Vygotsky's theory in 1978. The author deemed social interaction an essential element for cognitive learning and accorded great importance to learning in human thought development. To Vygotsky, learning is a cognitive activity that takes place in social interaction. By the same token, writing is a learning activity in which the writer learns best through interacting with his peer reviewers.

However, although there is a general belief that students' poor achievement in English essay writing could be traced to inappropriate methods of teaching adopted by teachers, it is likely that an intervening variable such as gender can also have some effects on the effectiveness of teaching method and learning outcome especially in English essay writing. Gender is

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There have been consistent reports of poor performance in the English language among Nigerian students over the years. Also, students' performance in the Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in the English language over the years has not been commendable. Students' performance in essay writing at Senior School Certificate Examinations has been generally poor. This low level of achievement has been attributed primarily to poor teaching methods. The method often used by English language teachers is the conventional method. This method makes students passive listeners in the class. More so, the conventional method does not allow teachers to adapt learning to the level of students' understanding (Ogunyomi, 2014). The poor performance of students in English essay writing may also be attributed to poor knowledge of Standard English. Many students could not express themselves in Standard English. Most students go straight into answering the questions without properly understanding them. Some of them are not well prepared for the Examination. It is evident that the major weakness of the students could be their inability to express themselves very well in Standard English (Akintunde & Angulu, 2020). Although the use of peer review technique has been tried in subjects like chemistry, government, social studies, and typewriting. However, its effectiveness is yet to be determined in the study of English language essay writing, and narrative essay in particular. Also, no study to the best of the researcher's knowledge explored the effect of the peer review technique on performance in English essay writing among secondary school students in Odigbo, Ondo State.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to find out the Effect of the Peer Review Technique on performance in English essay writing among secondary school students. Specifically, this study is aimed at:

1. Finding out the performance of students taught essay writing using the Peer Review Technique and those taught using the conventional method.
2. Determining the performance of male and female students taught essay writing using the Peer Review Technique and those taught using the conventional method.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the mean performance scores of students taught essay writing using the Peer Review Technique and those taught using the conventional method?
2. What is the effect of gender on the performance of students taught essay writing using the Peer Review Technique and those taught using the conventional method?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught essay writing using the Peer Review Technique and those taught using the conventional method.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught essay writing using the Peer Review Technique and those taught using the conventional method.

Methodology

A quasi-experimental research design was adopted for the study. Specifically, pretest a posttest non-equivalent groups design was used. This design was considered appropriate because intact classes were used by the researcher in order to avoid disruption of the normal academic programme of the schools. There are seventeen public secondary schools in this area. They are all co-educational schools. Four of these are located in urban areas while thirteen are located in rural areas respectively. The population of the study comprised all Senior Secondary class two (SS2) students in 2021. /2022 academic session in the seventeen government-owned secondary schools in Odigbo Local Government Area of Ondo State. The sample size for this study was 160 students comprising 78 male and 82 female students in Odigbo, Ondo, State. The study adopted a multi-stage

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sampling technique. A multi-stage sampling technique is a complex form of cluster sampling. It is one in which sampling is done sequentially across two or more hierarchical levels. The sampling technique was carried out in two stages. Purposive random sampling was used to select two schools from the local government (one in a rural area and one in an urban area) because the researcher had the freedom to select the schools that were appropriate for the study. The two schools that were selected by the researcher were fit for the purpose of the study because each of the schools is located in rural and urban areas respectively. The instrument for data collection was the Essay Writing Achievement Test (EWAT). This was adopted from WAEC's past questions. The essay Writing Achievement Test was only on narrative writing. The students were given an option to choose one of the six narrative essays. The researcher used the WAEC standard marking scheme. The minimum length expected in the essay was 450 words while the students were required to spend 45 minutes for the essay writing. The reliability of the instrument was established through trial testing on a group of 20 SSSII students using the Kendall coefficient of Concordance. The correlation coefficient of 0.71 was used as the reliability coefficient which showed that the instrument was relatively above average.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean performance score of students taught essay writing using the peer review technique and those taught using the conventional method?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of scores of students taught essay writing using peer review technique and those taught using conventional method.

Group	Number	Pre-test		post-test		Gain score
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Experimental	78	16.35	9.31	58.00	14.89	41.35
Control	82	16.28	5.87	43.46	12.40	27.18

Table 1 shows that the students who were taught essay writing using the peer review technique had a mean performance score of 58.00 with a standard deviation of 14.89 at the post-test while those who were taught the conventional method had a mean performance score of 43.46 with a standard deviation of 12.40. Mean gain scores of 41.35 and 27.18 for the two groups respectively imply that the students who were exposed to peer review technique achieved higher than their counterparts.

Research Question 2

What is the mean performance score of male and female students in English language essay writing taught using peer review technique?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of performance scores of male and female students in English language essay writing

Gender	Number	Pre-test		post-test		Gain score
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Male	82	15.06	9.08	45.46	15.32	30.40
Female	78	16.37	6.78	55.38	13.69	39.01

Table 2 revealed the mean performance scores of male and female students in essay writing. Male students had a post-test achievement mean score of 45.46 with a standard deviation of 15.52 while their female counterparts had a post-test achievement mean score of 55.38 with a standard deviation of 13.69. Gain scores of 30.40 and 39.01 for the male and female students respectively may have indicated that female students achieved higher than their male counterparts in English essay writing.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of students taught essay writing using peer review technique and those taught using conventional method.

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Table 3: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the effect of peer review technique on performance in English essay writing

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	16300.356 ^a	8	2037.545	14.177	.000
Intercept	48636.700	1	48636.700	338.420	.000
Pre-test	2142.645	1	2142.645	14.909	.000
Treatment	3818.277	1	3818.277	26.568	.000
Treatment * Gender	285.649	1	285.649	1.988	.161
Group * Gender *	19.161	1	19.161	.133	.716
Error	21701.244	151	143. 717		
Total	446850.000	160			
Corrected Total	38001.600	159			

a. R Squared = .429 (Adjusted R Squared = .399)

The analysis in Table 3 above shows that the probability associated with the calculated value of F (26.568) for the effect of peer review technique on performance in English essay writing is .000. Since the probability value of .000 is less than the .05 level of significance ($p < .05$), the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught essay writing using peer review techniques and those taught using conventional methods in favour of the experimental group.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students in English language essay writing.

Table 3 shows that the calculated value of F (13.780) for the influence of gender on performance in English essay writing is .098. This implies that gender is a significant factor in the student's performance in English essay writing since $p > .05$ in favour of the female students.

Discussion of Findings

The evidence from this study shows the higher performance of students taught English essay writing with the Peer Review Technique may be a result of many factors. One such factor according to Ajiwoju (2015) is making learning an interactive process and active, where the learner is totally immersed in learning activities that interest and appeal to him. Also, the fact that instruction was conducted in small heterogeneous peer learning groups which pared way for individual attention and equal participation might have contributed to the improved essay writing performance in the treatment group. These findings are consistent with the findings of Okika (2021) and Nwosu (2017), who believed that learners' interaction ginged their interest in writing which consequently increased higher performance in essay writing.

The higher performance of female students may be as a result of interactions among the students. The findings agree with the findings of Ali (2016) and Ajiwoju (2015) which indicated that gender was significant in students' performance in the English Language.

Conclusion

Peer Review Technique has been found to be effective in promoting performance in English essay writing. The mean performance scores of the students taught with Peer Review were found to be higher. Also, the students taught with the Peer Review Technique were found to be more interested and motivated than those taught with the conventional method.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study;

1. Secondary school teachers should make use of the Peer Review Technique in teaching essay writing.
2. Teacher trainers in the various universities and colleges of education should incorporate the Peer Review Technique as a useful technique in second language teaching and learning and train the teacher trainees on how to use the technique.

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